

Tier 1 (Green)

In your opinion, did Brexit influence the GDPR implementation? If yes, how?

You are a researcher organizing genetic data for clinical trials. As you carry on your data wrangling you realize a consent form is missing. How should you proceed?

You are an athlete using a fitness tracking app. The app requests information that is completely unrelated to the service it is providing, after you complete the paid registration. How should you react?

You found out that your (personal) data was used without your consent on a website/product/service. What will be your next step? Will you contact any authority at regional/national/EU level?

You have reached XY website. The company is asking permission to access your location in real time to provide better recommendations closer to you. What are you going to do? Why?

Welcome to XYZ social media. For us to deliver the best services we ask you to provide your consent for sharing your personal data, statistical data and functional data with external providers. What are you going to do? Will you agree or not, why?

You applied to a private healthcare provider located in the EU. When they took down your personal information, they also asked for your phone number and said this information is needed to contact you about your test results and inform you about special campaigns. Would you agree to give them your phone number, why?

You sign up for a research activity after ordering a DNA test to your home. The research is aimed at generating health recommendations based on your exercise and diet data. After a while, you change your mind and want to quit the research, but the company representative says that you cannot quit at this point. Would you agree with the company representative's words, why?

Tier 2 (Blue)

You received your blood count test results after your visit to the hospital, but you noticed they were not your results but someone else's with the same name and surname as you. You contacted the hospital and asked them to correct the mistake, but you have been told that once the test results are finalized, they cannot be amended. Would you agree with the hospital officer's statement, why?

You received an email from an unknown colleague who presumably works in a different department. The mail does not ask for any confidential information, but it does ask to provide information about the software and hardware specifications of your working station. What would you do in that situation? How could you try to verify the identity of the person requesting information?

You are a clinical trial coordinator in a biotechnology startup that processes health data. One of your data analysts suggests that a few patients at a clinical trial your company is carrying out may be at risk of cardiovascular disease, a finding which is unrelated to your service that patients consented for. Should you approach the patients? If so, how?

The provider of a digital service is rolling up slowly the two-factor authentication (2FA) mechanism to increase security and ensure privacy for its users. However, it requires you to provide a mobile phone number to receive a one-time PIN code expiring in a limited time (e.g., 15 seconds). What are you going to do? Will you agree to provide your number and why?

A big tech company has decided to challenge the EC regarding the applicability of the DMA. They believe this regulation doesn't apply to them since their service/platform is not so popular in Europe. What is your opinion on this? Do you believe users should have the right to select pre-installed apps on their devices even though these are provided from external third parties?

When you were in your local pharmacist to collect your medication, the pharmacist offered to give your next-door neighbor's medications who also has a chronic illness. When you asked how the pharmacist knew where you lived, he/she mentioned that it is accessible from the database that they

have been using. Do you think that is there something wrong with his/her actions about sharing your neighbor's medical information with you, why?

You are designing a psychology study to be performed on students where you examine the effect of sleep on anxiety. In your form you want to be as comprehensive as possible to design an optimal study and analysis. However, you are aware that the ethics committee may not be lenient with asking questions that are too personal or may be deemed irrelevant to the study, hence you wish to adhere to data minimization. What criteria will you use to decide what risk factors to include in your study?

You are applying for a job and are required to complete a psychometric test. You feel that the questions regarding lifestyle, personal information and emotional management are becoming too personal and are curious as to how the employer will utilize this information. As an applicant what rights do you have regarding this information that is collected? What type of information does it classify as?

You are using an app to manage the heating, lighting and security in your house. You learn of a breach in the app database, where customers data was compromised. The company has not contacted you regarding the breach and you had to learn from the news instead. What responsibilities do you think the company should have? What steps should you take if the company does not resolve/take responsibility for the breach?

You are using a social networking app. Concerning news regarding its new CEO and novel data management regulations changes cause you to be disappointed with the app and wish to leave but retain your pictures and past uploads. How should you proceed? What would you do if the app allows you to disable your account but retains your information? Is the uploaded information yours to claim?

Your employer is asking you to fill in a form regarding your personal information for company insurance purposes. You realize the questions are too personal and think that some of them may be classified as sensitive information (i.e., health, religion, ethnicity, sexual orientation). What kind of information do you think is sensitive? Does your employer have the right to demand this type of information in the workplace setting? Why is this data different from data such as your name and age?

Tier 3 (Red)

You have been using a Fitness app to keep track of your workouts and meals. You recently heard about a new app with more advanced features and want to try it out. Instead of starting from scratch, you remembered that you have the right to take personal data with you. So, you asked the app provider's customer services to give you a copy of all your data (including workouts and meals data) stored in the app. You received an email saying that your request cannot be doable. Would you agree with the email that you received, why?

You notice that a colleague from your work often takes confidential documents home. While it is against the policy of the company you work in, upon your inquiry, your colleague just shrugs it off, telling you that "he was doing it for years now". Although you do not want to cause any problems to him and his evaluation in the company, you notice that those documents concern your customer base and allow for the re-identification of people engaged in a clinical trial that is still ongoing. How would you deal with such a situation?

Upon examination of the clinical trial results, you fail to notice that you uploaded them to your personal cloud (assume that the cloud uploads all your files that were downloaded to your personal computer). After the clinical trials end, you notice that the cloud provider reported a series of security breaches, and your data was probably comprised as a result. Taking that into consideration, it is highly probable that all the information about the clinical trial (including patients' personal data) was also compromised as a result. Elaborate on your code of conduct.

Because your team was assigned a project that was long overdue, you worked overtime for more than a week. On a Friday afternoon, you receive a phone call from a person who allegedly works on the same project. You are asked to share confidential information (i.e., credentials) that allow them to establish an SSH connection to your company's server. Without thinking much – and tired by the ongoing crunch – you just provide them with a default login and a password. After the connections hangs up, you just realize your mistake. What would you do next?

You work in a middle-sized company as a data engineer. It is your first week in this job and you basically don't know anyone yet. As you carry

instructions provided by HR to finish your setup, you notice that all your servers' set-up follow a very strange Privilege Access Management (PAM). More precisely, all the new users are operating on a super-user account basis with all the root privileges. You start to worry about this, as you know it amounts to a high-security risk. How would you proceed?

You are working in the HR office of an international firm and are analyzing location and performance data for employees. You realize you are meant to adhere to certain principles to be a lawful data controller and data processor. Considering data is collected from multiple countries (some of which are not subject to the European regulations) which regulations should you adhere to? Which principles characterize data controller and data processor responsibilities?

You are a guard at a prison where AI is used to assess the chance of recidivism in use. You realize that the algorithm consistently assesses individuals of certain ethnicities to be at greater risk of recidivism which leads to less favorable outcomes for them in terms of parole and bail. Your observation is anecdotal at this point, but you have faith the status quo is unjust and wish to take action. What would you do? Is it the algorithm, the software developers or the management who is responsible for the unequal treatment of prisoners?

There is a new global health crisis, and it is rapidly threatening an increasing number of lives. You are working in the Ministry of Health and are designing an algorithm to trace the disease in order to manage prevention. The public is hesitant to participate due to the spread of misinformation and bypassing certain privacy laws might be beneficial in the process of saving lives. Does the right to health take precedence over privacy? How would you incentivize reluctant individuals to participate in the attempt to control the disease?

You work in a cybersecurity firm. You are outsourced by a hospital to categorize and protect their EHR data. In this process the firm grants you access to all their data. Do you have the right to complete access to non-anonymized data? What factors should you consider when assessing security for health data compared to other types of data?